

Metachromasia of Pseudoisocyanine

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Pseudoisocyanine in the presence of λ -carrageenan gives a very sharp absorption band towards the longer wave length side of its normal absorption band; large excess of the carrageenan facilitates the appearance of the band. This spectral change is just opposite to what is observed with the common metachromatic dyes. However, reagents like urea, ethanol etc., interfere with the appearance of this band similar to metachromasia. The appearance of this red-shifted band has been interpreted as the reversal of metachromasia due to the binding of the dye cations to the polyanion without dye-dye interaction. Spectra of mixtures of pseudoisocyanine and common metachromatic dyes like crystal violet acridine orange, pinacyanol have been described.

Spectrophotometrically metachromasia means the shift of the normal absorption band of the dye that is observed in dilute aqueous solution towards shorter wave length and with reduced absorbance in presence of chromotropes. With pseudoisocyanine, however, a new sharp band appears at longer wave length under similar conditions¹. This new band has higher absorbance compared to the normal absorption band, which suffers only a small decrease in its absorbance with the appearance of the new band. The spectral changes undergone by this dye is thus just opposite to what is observed with the common metachromatic dyes. It is desirable to think now whether the same causes that are responsible for the blue shift with the other dyes are operative in case of pseudoisocyanine and whether the appearance of this sharp band at longer wave length in presence of polyanions should be classed under metachromasia at all. Bean, Shepherd, Kay and Walwick² also observed the appearance of a new band at longer wave length with the dye-4-5-4'-5'-dibenzo-3-3'-diethyl-9-methyl thiocarbocyanine (DBTC) and expressed the view that this new band at longer wave length is due to the reaction of the individual dye molecules at isolated sites and without dye-dye interaction. The apparent similarity between the α' -band³ that is observed with the common metachromatic dyes only in the presence of large excess of chromotropes and this new band—called the J-band—also leads to a similar thinking. But while the α' -band is only red-shifted by 10–15 $m\mu$, the J-band appears at about 70–80 $m\mu$ towards the longer wave length side of the normal absorption band of pseudoisocyanine or DBTA. Alternatively if it is assumed that pseudoisocyanine is aggregated or dimerised in dilute aqueous solution and the binding of the individual dyes at the anionic sites of the chromotrope causes an effective disgregation, then the appearance of the J-band at longer wave length and also with enhanced absorbance could be interpreted as reversal of metachromasia. The purpose of the present report is to describe the alleged metachromasia of pseudoisocyanine, mixtures of pseudoisocyanine and other common metachromatic dyes.

1. Von W. Appel and G. Scheibe, *Z. Naturforsch.*, 1958, **13b**, 359.
2. R. C. Bean, W. C. Shepherd, R. E. Kay and E. R. Walwick, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1965, **69**, 4368.
3. A. L. Stone and D. F. Bradley, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 3627.

EXPERIMENTAL

The dye N-N'-diethyl pseudoisocyanine was obtained as gift from Agfa, Germany and was used as such. Sources and purifications of the other dyes as well as of the chromotropes have been described⁴. Spectra were read with the Hilger Uvispek spectrophotometer, model H. 700 using 1 cm cells. The organic solvents and urea were reagent grade, E. Merk products, and were used without any further purifications.

RESULTS

Schiebler⁵ working with oxidised insulin as the chromotrope reported that pseudoisocyanine gave the metachromatic, or rather the J-band, if the concentration of the dye was not less than $1 \times 10^{-4} M$. Appel and Scheibe¹ also worked with $10^{-4} M$ dye in studying the metachromasia of pseudoisocyanine with chromotropes like chondroitin sulfate. Figure 1

Figure-1

Absorption spectra of pseudoisocyanine ($1.00 \times 10^{-5} M$) in presence of different concentrations of chondroitin sulfate (CS); A, —O—O—O—, CS, nil; B, —●—●—●—, 2×10^{-5} equiv./l; C, —△—△—△—, 5×10^{-5} equiv./l; D, ———, 20×10^{-5} equiv./l.

shows the spectra of pseudo-isocyanine, $1 \times 10^{-5} M$ in water and in the presence of chondroitin sulfate. It is apparent that there is no change in the shape of the absorption spectra of the dye due to the presence of chondroitin sulfate, only the absorbance over almost the whole region is reduced. But with λ -carrageenan as the chromotrope, $1 \times 10^{-5} M$ pseudoisocyanine exhibits spectral change (Figure-2), a new sharp band appears at $575 m\mu$. Since this new band is at longer wave length side of the α -band of the dye, it is referred to as the J-band and differentiated from the μ -band that occurs at the shorter wave length in case of the common metachromatic dyes. The absorbance at the J-band increases with increasing amounts of λ -carrageenan even when the polyelectrolyte to dye ratio (P/D) is 120. Figure-2 (upper half)

4. M. K. Pal and M. Schubert, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, **84**, 4384.

5. T. H. Schiebler and S. Schiesster, *Histochemie*, 1959, **1**, 445.

shows the spectra of the dye pinacyanol, the higher homologue of pseudoisocyanine, in water and in presence of λ -carrageenan. It is obvious that pinacyanol gives the sharp metachro-

Figure-2

Upper half: Spectra of pinacyanol ($1.00 \times 10^{-5} M$) in presence of different concentrations of λ -carrageenan ($\lambda-C$); A, ---O---O---O--- , $\lambda-C$, O; B, $\text{---}\Delta\text{---}\Delta\text{---}\Delta\text{---}$, $\lambda-C$, 1.2×10^{-5} equiv./l; C, $\text{---}\bullet\text{---}\bullet\text{---}\bullet\text{---}$, $\lambda-C$, 20×10^{-5} equiv./l.

Lower half: Spectra of pseudoisocyanine ($1.00 \times 10^{-5} M$) in presence of different concentrations of λ -carrageenan ($\lambda-C$), A, ---O---O---O--- , $\lambda-C$, O; B, $\text{---}\bullet\text{---}\bullet\text{---}\bullet\text{---}$, $\lambda-C$, 1×10^{-5} , equiv./l, C, $\text{---}\Delta\text{---}\Delta\text{---}\Delta\text{---}$, $\lambda-C = 20 \times 10^{-5}$ equiv./l; D, $\text{---}\square\text{---}\square\text{---}\square\text{---}$, $\lambda-C$, 130×10^{-5} equiv./l.

Figure-3

Upper half: Spectra of mixture of pseudoisocyanine and pinacyanol in presence of λ -carrageenan, each dye $1.00 \times 10^{-5} M$, P/D = 1.2; A, $\text{---}\bullet\text{---}\bullet\text{---}\bullet\text{---}$, additive spectra; B, ---O---O---O--- , experimental spectra; C, $\text{---}\cdot\text{---}\cdot\text{---}\cdot\text{---}$, difference between B and A (right hand axis).

Lower half: Same as upper half with acridine orange in place of pinacyanol.

matic band at shorter wave length with λ -carrageenan at the chromotrope. Also with the appearance of the metachromatic band, the absorbance of the α -band of the dye drops substantially. Pinacyanol also exhibits metachromasia with chondroitin sulfate as chromotrope. Figure-3 (upper half) shows the spectra of mixture of pseudoisocyanine and pinacyanol, each dye at $1.0 \times 10^{-5} M$ in presence of λ -carrageenan. This spectra is quite different from the additive spectra (Curve A) that is calculated from the spectra of the individual dyes in presence of λ -carrageenan. There is negative deviation all along the range of wave lengths studied except at the two ends. Figure-3 (lower half) depicts the results of similar studies with pseudoisocyanine and acridine orange mixture. Crystal violet and pseudoisocyanine mixture also exhibits similar deviations.

The effects of ethanol and urea on the spectra of pseudoisocyanine alone or in the presence of λ -carrageenan were studied. In presence of 80% ethanol and 8M urea, the J-band disappears; and the spectra becomes identical with the spectra of the dye alone in the respective solvents. In 90% v/v ethanol, formamide, dioxane, tertiary butanol and 8M urea, the spectra of $1 \times 10^{-5} M$ pseudoisocyanine is similar to the spectra of the aqueous solution of the dye, only the absorbance in the solvents is 15-30% higher compared to that in water.

DISCUSSION

From the comparison of the Figures 1 and 2 it is apparent that the appearance of the J-band of pseudoisocyanine in the presence of a suitable chromotrope is different from the μ -band that is obtained with the common metachromatic dyes under similar conditions: (i) the J-band appears at the longer wave length side of the normal absorption band of the dye, (ii) the appearance of the J-band is associated with relatively small decrease in the absorbance at the α -band of the dye, whereas in true metachromasia the α -band drops substantially, (iii) the J-band is narrow and has higher absorbance than the α -band while the μ -band is broad and with reduced absorbance (iv) with dye less than $10^{-4} M$, the J-band does not appear with chondroitin sulfate, though chondroitin sulfate has been described as a strong chromotrope⁴. Yet the effects of solvents like ethanol, urea, dioxane, tertiary butanol etc., on the spectra of the dye or its J-band are similar to their effects on the spectra of dye like acridine orange⁴. It has been observed that 8M urea or aqueous ethanol destroys the J-band of pseudoisocyanine developed in the presence of λ -carrageenan and the spectra resembles the spectra of the dye in the respective solvents. Spectra of $1 \times 10^{-5} M$ dye in solvents like 90% v/v ethanol, formamide, dioxane, tert.-butanol and 8M urea are similar to the spectra of the aqueous solution of the dye, the peaks are at 490 $m\mu$ and 525 $m\mu$ except in case of formamide where both the peaks are red shifted by 5 $m\mu$. In all these solvents the absorbances at the peaks are higher compared to when water is the solvent. These solvents are known to disaggregate dye molecules and dyes obey Beer's law in these solvents in the concentration range where they disobey the law in aqueous solution⁶. If the appearance of the J-band in the presence chromotrope were due to the effective disaggregation of the dye molecules due to the individual binding to the anionic sites, then these solvents were

6. M. Schubert and D. Hamerman, *J. Histochem. Cytochem.*, 1956, 4, 159.

also expected to cause disaggregation with the appearance of the J-band. But J-band was missing in these solvents. Bean² *et al.* report that the pure J-band with DBTC is obtained coincident with a degree of esterification of some polyacids which would create an average spacing between anion sites just slightly greater than the full length of the dye molecules. It is also apparent from the Figure 2 that the production of the J-band of pseudoisocyanine in presence of λ -carrageenan is facilitated by large excess of the latter. Even then the spectral shift could not be assigned wholly to the binding of the dye cations to the polyanion, this is expected to cause the red-shift by 10–15 $m\mu$ only. Soda and Yoshioka⁷ have shown from the measurement of electrical double refraction of polyelectrolyte combined with metachromatic dyes, that the dyes are bound to the polyelectrolyte even when the excess of the latter has caused the disappearance of metachromasia and the band was shifted to longer wave length side of the α -band. This red shift, which is usually 10–15 $m\mu$, may be assigned to the binding of individual dye molecules to the chromotrope without dye-dye interaction. If it is assumed that the pseudoisocyanine molecules are aggregated (or dimerised) even in $10^{-5} M$ concentration then binding of the individual dye molecules would be an effective disaggregation and the appearance of the J-band at the longer wave length side of the normal absorption band of the dye by about 70 $m\mu$ could be interpreted. If this were the case then some of the solvents mentioned should have been able to disaggregate the dye molecules provided the nature of bonds involved in the aggregation of the pseudoisocyanine molecules were the same in case of the dyes like acridine orange, crystal violet etc. In case of the latter dyes hydrophobic bonds were thought to be involved in aggregation^{8–10}.

Rohatgi and Singhal¹¹ suggested that both hydrophobic and hydrogen bonding may be involved in demerization of dye, depending upon the nature of the dye. Whether pseudoisocyanine is aggregated in dilute aqueous solution like congo-red has to be investigated as well as the nature of bonding in the aggregation.

Some metachromatic dyes form hetero-aggregates^{12–14} as is revealed by characteristic deviations of the metachromatic spectra of mixture of such dyes from the additive spectra. If both the dyes are truly metachromatic and form heteroaggregates the difference spectra shows a positive deviation around the absorption band of the dye having absorption band at shorter wave length, whereas a negative deviation at the absorption region of the other dye¹³. Levshin and Suvorov¹⁵ working with mixture of crystal violet and rhodamine 6G,

7. T. Soda and K. Yoshioka, *Nippon Kagaku Zasshi*, 1965, **86**, 1019.
8. M. K. Pal and M. Schubert, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, **84**, 4384.
9. P. Mukherjee and A. K. Ghosh, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1963, **67**, 193.
10. M. K. Pal, *Histochemie*, 1965, **5**, 24.
11. K. K. Rohatgi and G. S. Singhal, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1966, **70**, 1695.
12. H. L. Booji and W. A. Loeven, *Arch. intern. physiol.*, 1954, **62**, 552.
13. M. K. Pal and M. Schubert, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1963, **67**, 1821.
14. W. West and S. Pearce, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1965, **69**, 1894.
15. L. V. Levshin and V. S. Suvorov, *Opt. i. Spektroskopiya*, 1958, **4**, 678.

the latter dye being non-metachromatic, reported negative deviation in the difference curve without pronounced peaks. The appearance of the difference curves shown in the Figure 3 with pseudoisocyanine as one dye seems to be more similar to this description rather than the ones reported by Pal and Schubert¹³ where both the dyes in the mixtures were truly metachromatic. This also gives indication that pseudoisocyanine, like rhodamine 6G, may not be a metachromatic dye.

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